

Rewarding and recognising Team Infrastructure Roles

Arielle Bennett
Programme Manager

[@biotechchat](https://twitter.com/biotechchat)
abennett@turing.ac.uk

Esther Plomp
Data Steward

[@toothfairy](https://twitter.com/toothfairy)
e.plomp@tudelft.nl

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A Manifesto for Rewarding and Recognising Team Infrastructure Roles

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Arielle Bennett

Programme Manager

[@biotechchat](#)
abennett@turing.ac.uk

Tom Hostler

Senior Lecturer in Psychology

[@tomhostler](#)
t.hostler@mmu.ac.uk

**Ismael Kherroubi
Garcia**

Research Governance Consultant

[@hermeneuticist](#)
ismael@kairoi.uk

Hao Ye

Reproducibility Librarian

[@hao_and_y](#)
haoye@ufl.edu

**Cassandra Gould van
Praag**

Open Science Community Manager

[@cassgvp](#)
cassandra.gouldvanpraag@psyc
h.ox.ac.uk

Sam Teplitzky

Open Science Librarian

[@samteplitzky](#)
samteplitzky@berkeley.edu

Antonio Schettino

Senior Advisor Open Science

[@antonioschettino](#)
schettino@eur.nl

Esther Plomp

Data Steward

[@toothfairyt](#)
e.plomp@tudelft.nl

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Who or what are "Team Infrastructure Roles"?

laboratory technicians,
project managers, grant
officers, finance managers,
privacy officers, patent
officers, internal review
board members, librarians,
programme manager, IP
managers, data stewards,
data managers, community
managers, research
software engineers, data
wranglers ...

[Whitaker 2023](#)

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Team Infrastructure Roles (TIRs)

Those who **contribute** to the research process but who are not **incentivised** by participation in the credit economy (AKA academic papers)

They play a **structural** role in the research process

Benefits of TIRs for research

- ✓ Increased specialist expertise
- ✓ Ability to tackle more complex challenges
- ✓ More diverse perspectives contributing to research
- ✓ Improved productivity and processes

“We can't expect individuals to be able to perform all the tasks [of academia] to the highest standard”

- Kirstie Whitaker, 2023

“Passing those tasks to professionals may be viewed as “a hollowing out of [...] what it means [...] to be an academic”

(MacFarlane, 2011, p. 71)

Our perspectives

Arielle Bennett
Programme
Manager

Esther Plomp
Data Steward

Esther Plomp

- ✓ **Data Steward** Delft University of Technology
- ✓ **Project member** The Turing Way
- ✓ **Mentor/expert** Open Life Science
- ✓ **Open Research Ambassador and Board member** IsoArch

Arielle Bennett

- ✓ **Programme Manager** The Alan Turing Institute
- ✓ **Project member** The Turing Way
- ✓ **Mentor** Open Life Science
- ✓ **International Officer** United Tech & Allied Workers

Emerging Challenges

- ✓ Lack of autonomy
- ✓ Limited formalisation of career pathways
- ✓ Prejudice against TIR activities and career choices
- ✓ Recognition of TIR contributions

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Our envisioned future

Pathways forward

Focus on the **process**, not the outcomes

An expansive system for **recognising contributions**

A system to **validate research outputs**

Standardised roles and pathways for **career development**

The Turing Way: Contribute Your Role!

Research Infrastructure Roles

In summary

- ✓ TIRs provide diverse benefits to research processes and outputs
- ✓ Challenges with TIRs include autonomy, development, and mutual respect
- ✓ Focusing beyond papers to processes and broader outputs will benefit those working in TIRs

How should we remake the system so that diverse roles are truly seen as integral participants in research?

Thank you!

- ✓ Our co-authors!
- ✓ *The Turing Way*, OLS, and wider open science communities
- ✓ [Turing Way illustrations by Scriberia](#)
- ✓ The Tools, Practices & Systems Programme at The Alan Turing Institute

